

THE ORIGINS AND DEVELOPMENT OF SCIENTIFIC MANAGEMENT

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ABSTRACT

This article addresses the origin and development of Scientific Management, a theory proposed by F. W. Taylor. Bibliographical research was conducted, consulting journals and books by recognized authors in the field. The three main questions guiding the research were: what is the origin and development of Scientific Management, what is the theoretical proposition of this approach, and who were its main followers. It was found that, before Taylor, several authors had already suggested ideas aligned with the principles of Scientific Management, including Adam Smith (1776), Robert Owen (1810), James Mill (1820), Charles Babbage (1832), Frederick Halsey (1891), Daniel McCallum (1856), Henry V. Poor (1812-1905), Henry Metcalfe (1885), and Henry Towne (1886). Scientific Management advocates the specialization and division of labor as strategies to increase worker productivity and company profitability. The main followers of this theory were Henry Gantt (1861-1919), Carl Barth (1860-1939), Sanford E. Thompson (1867–1949), Harrington Emerson (1853-1931), Frank B. Gilbreth (1868-1924), Lilian Gilbreth (1878-1972), Morris L. Cooke (1872-1960), and Henry Ford (1863-1947).

Keywords: Scientific Management, F.W. Taylor, Rational Work Design, Time-motion, Human Resources, Administration.

The principal object of management should be to secure the maximum prosperity for the employer, coupled with the maximum prosperity for each employee.

Principles of Scientific Management, F.W. Taylor (1911)

INTRODUCTION

This article discusses the origin and development of the management model known as Scientific Management, or Taylorism, in the early 20th century. It is a theory developed by the American mechanical engineer Frederick Winslow Taylor, based on the application of the scientific method to ensure productive efficiency through the rationalization of labor. Its goal is to increase worker productivity and the profitability and prosperity of both companies and workers. According to Chiavenato (2014, p. 100), the greatest contribution of Scientific Management was

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mass production, successfully applied by Henry Ford. The foundational work of this movement is *Principles of Scientific Management*, considered by Bedeian and Wren (2001, as cited in Wren, 2011, p. 12) to be the most influential of the 20th century.

In this context, three central questions were established to guide the present study: 1) What is the origin of this approach? 2) What characterizes Scientific Management? 3) Who were the main followers of this theory?

To carry out this study, bibliographic research was conducted in specialized publications by authors such as Chiavenato, Filho, Da Silva, C. B. Thompson, Urwick, Wren, Wrege, as well as the works of F. W. Taylor.

SCIENTIFIC MANAGEMENT ORIGINS

Frederick Winslow Taylor (1856-1915), a mechanical engineer and business consultant born in Philadelphia, is widely recognized as the father of Scientific Management. His professional career began at Midvale Steel, where he rose to the position of chief engineer. It was in this company that Taylor initiated his investigations into labor management, developing and testing the administrative methods that would become the foundation of his theory. Later, he worked at Bethlehem Steel Company, where he further developed his practices and theories.

The first work in which Taylor presented his ideas was the article *Price Rating System* (1895), followed by more comprehensive books, such as *Shop Management* (1903) and *Principles of Scientific Management* (1911), which solidified his contributions to scientific management. The latter, especially, became the seminal work of the movement, profoundly influencing management in the 20th century.

In addition to his career as an engineer and consultant, Taylor served as president of the American Society of Mechanical Engineers (ASME) in 1906 and was a lecturer at Harvard University's Business School from 1909 to 1914, where he shared his theories with a wider audience. His innovative approach, focused on efficiency, task division, and labor specialization, forever changed the way management and production were viewed and practiced in the industries of his time.

The new approach of Scientific Management emerged at the beginning of the 20th century, a period marked by rapid industrial development but also by a great lack of administrative

knowledge among business owners and managers. In this context, the migration of the rural population to cities created an abundance of labor available for the new industries, while the demand for industrial products increased significantly.

It was in this context that Taylor proposed methods to improve company productivity, focusing on enhancing the efficiency of production processes. His goal was to reduce material waste, rationalize work methods, and simultaneously increase workers' well-being by ensuring that production standards were raised without compromising the health and safety of the workforce. The implementation of these practices aimed not only to optimize production but also to provide a balance between the interests of companies and workers' well-being, creating a relationship of mutual benefit.

Taylor's proposal was revolutionary and quickly spread to various countries around the world. According to Gross, as cited by Da Silva (2001, p. 119), Taylor's new theory was characterized by the following key aspects: work analysis, standardization of tools, worker selection and training, supervision and planning of activities, and payment by production. These elements formed the foundation of Scientific Management, which sought to optimize production processes, ensure greater work efficiency, and, at the same time, promote greater specialization of tasks and improvement of working conditions.

However, several researchers point out that, long before Taylor, various authors had already made administrative proposals aimed at improving the efficiency and earnings of organizations and workers. In this sense, Urwick (1949, p. 31) states that, as early as 1786, James Watt (1736-1819), inventor of the steam engine, had implemented a technical training policy for employees at his factory, The Soho Foundry. In doing so, the company ensured that its workforce was qualified to produce the various parts needed for steam engines. Moreover, Watt and his partner, Matthew Boulton, adopted the system of payment by results in their company, encouraging productivity through remuneration tied to individual and collective performance.

Later, Roll, as cited by Urwick (1949, p. 31), comments that "during the early years of its existence, Soho became the training center for skilled workmen, and a laboratory of new processes."

According to Silva (2011, p. 56), and corroborating Roll's statements, Taylor began to systematize the principles of Scientific Management in 1900. However, similar ideas had been proposed earlier by other authors. One example is the Scottish economist Adam Smith (1723-1790), who, in his work *The Wealth of Nations* (1776), discussed the specialization of labor, forms

of control, and remuneration policies. According to Da Silva (2001, p. 103), Smith's ideas on the division of labor were fundamental for the simplification of production processes and time studies.

Subsequently, Lodi (op. cit.) highlights that, in 1810, social reformer Robert Owen (1771-1858) advocated for proper worker training and introduced the concept of the "silent monitor," a work evaluation system based on a color-coded system. In 1820, James Mill (1773-1836) delved into the analysis of human movements during task execution, a precursor to studies that would become crucial in the field of ergonomics.

Moreover, English mathematician and engineer Charles Babbage (1792-1871) was another precursor of Scientific Management. In 1832, he advocated for the use of the scientific method at work, emphasizing specialization, the social division of labor, and the study of human fatigue. Babbage also proposed a profit-sharing system for companies and a bonus for workers who presented effective suggestions for improving processes in their workshops.

Finally, Lodi (op. cit.) mentions engineer Frederick Halsey (1856-1935), author of the article *The Premium Plan of Paying for Labor* (1891), which suggested implementing bonuses in the wages of skilled workers, a proposal aimed at encouraging productivity and work quality.

Other authors mentioned by Da Silva (2001, p. 104) include engineer Daniel McCallum (1856), who proposed the precise description of tasks and positions as an essential condition for effective administration, and who also created the first organizational chart. Another noteworthy figure is financial analyst Henry Varnum Poor (1812-1905), a pioneer in suggesting the creation of a "system" of administration based on a well-planned organizational structure, complemented by an adequate communication and information system, to keep management constantly updated on the company's situation.

Additionally, Captain Henry Metcalfe (1847-1917) published, in 1885, the book *The Cost of Manufactures and the Administration of Workshops, Public and Private*, a work considered pioneering in the field of industrial management. In turn, Henry Towne (1844-1924) published the article *The Engineer as an Economist* (1886) in the *American Society of Mechanical Engineers* (ASME). In both works, the authors addressed ideas and concerns that converge with Taylor's proposals, highlighting the importance of rational and systematic management in the industrial context.

THE THEORY OF SCIENTIFIC MANAGEMENT

What, then, is Scientific Management? Initially, Taylor called his new system the *Piece-rate System*. Later, he changed the name to *Task-system* and eventually published his seminal book, adopting the term *Scientific Management*—a concept that, although widely associated with him, was not actually created by Taylor.

Indeed, the term *Scientific Management* is attributed to lawyer Louis Dembitz Brandeis (Silva, 2011, p. 15). In 1910, a group of railway companies requested an increase in existing tariffs from the Interstate Commerce Commission to cover the costs arising from wage increases for their workers. During the inquiry, representatives of the companies, who were opposed to the increase, hired Brandeis as their attorney. In his argument before the Commission, Brandeis contended that the companies could afford the wage increase if they adopted a more efficient administrative management. It was in this context that the concept of the "Taylor system" emerged, also referred to as *Task Management* or *Modern Methods of Management*, as Taylor's method was known at the time (Wren, 2011, p. 16).

Brandeis successfully demonstrated, based on Emerson's analysis, that applying Taylorist principles in the railway companies could generate a savings of one million dollars per day, leading to his case's victory. The term *Scientific Management* emerged after a commission of engineers, convened by Brandeis, recommended this name. Among the members of this commission were several well-known Taylorists, such as Gantt, Gilbreth, and Emerson. They based their recommendation on the fundamental characteristic of Taylor's method: "the use of research—the scientific method par excellence—as a criterion for the study and solution of management issues" (op. cit.).

Before the publication of his second book, *Principles of Scientific Management*, Taylor preferred the term *Task Management*, as he considered *Scientific Management* too academic to be accepted by managers and business owners (Chiavenato, 2014). However, the term *Scientific Management* became widely known and commonly used after significant press coverage of the trial before the Interstate Commerce Commission.

Chiavenato (2014, pp. 80-82) divides Taylor's work into two periods. The first corresponds to the publication of *Shop Management* in 1903, and the second to the publication of *Principles of Scientific Management* in 1911. The term *Shop Management* refers to the organization of work in factories. Taylor proposed the rationalization of labor through motion-time studies, based on human anatomy and physiology. His idea was that once the correct time to produce an item and

the quantity that could be produced daily were determined, the challenge would be to ensure that the worker maintained this pace. Taylor believed that workers intentionally produced below their maximum capacity, a practice he called *soldiering*, translated as “systematic loafing.”

The motion-time study went through two phases (Da Silva, 2011, p. 120): the analytical phase and the constructive phase. In the first, each task was subdivided into basic movements. The most suitable and efficient movements were selected, timed, and recorded, while the useless movements were eliminated. In the constructive phase, these elementary movements and their times were standardized to define the best way of working in the workshops.

Taylor proposed several innovations, such as wages based on productivity, the creation of standards and rules for work, the selection of workers according to their aptitudes, proper training, and the creation of good working conditions. He also suggested the use of scientific principles for workshop management, the requirement of a minimum output for each worker, the standardization of work by supervisors, and the social division of labor (Silva, 2011, pp. 62-63). Additionally, Taylor assigned the responsibility for setting standards, selecting and training personnel, and providing incentives to the supervisors. Taylor’s book became a practical manual for managers of the time.

In the second book, Taylor asserts that the rationalization of work must be accompanied by a general restructuring of the company. According to him, companies faced problems such as workers' systematic loafing, the management's lack of knowledge about work routines and the time needed to perform tasks, and the lack of standardization of techniques and methods used. Taylor proposed *Scientific Management* as the solution to these problems.

Taylor estimated that each worker produced only one-third of their capacity. He identified three reasons for this systematic loafing. The first was related to workers' belief that they should be in solidarity with their colleagues, fearing that if productivity increased, many could be laid off. At the time, it was common to think that technological improvements would result in job losses. The second reason was the inefficiency of managerial systems, which did not define the time required for each task, leading workers to reduce production to protect their interests. The third reason identified by Taylor was the use of empirical work methods (rule-of-thumb), passed down from one generation of workers to the next without technical or scientific basis. Workers learned by observing their colleagues, which resulted in slow and inefficient task execution, wasting time and effort (Taylor, 1919, pp. 15-26).

Taylor argued that management should take a more active role in training and guiding workers, as well as providing appropriate incentives to stimulate productivity. According to Taylor, it was the responsibility of managers—rather than workers—to design activities within the

workshops systematically and efficiently, avoiding practices based solely on empirical experience (Da Silva, 2001, p. 118).

The foundations of the Rational Organization of Work, proposed by Taylor in his second book, include the following guidelines (Chiavenato, 2014, pp. 84-94):

- Work analysis and time-motion study to define the best work method (the best one way) and the standard time for its execution. Later, Frank Gilbreth concluded that every task could be reduced to basic movements.
- Anatomical and physiological study of human fatigue, aiming to execute useful movements in a sequential and appropriate manner, eliminating unnecessary movements. Gilbreth also contributed with proposals regarding workplace arrangement, tools, and equipment used to optimize movement efficiency.
- Division of labor, specialization of workers, and functional supervision, which led to the creation of the assembly line. Each employee should focus on a single operation or task in a continuous and repetitive manner, promoting specialization. This way, several workers performed different parts of the overall task in parallel or in series.
- Job and task design. The task refers to any specific activity performed by the worker, while the job is the set of tasks performed continuously. Job design improved productivity, facilitated supervision, and reduced training costs.
- Standardization of methods and tools, which included processes, machines, raw materials, and components. This allowed the company to reduce waste and be more efficient.
- Adequate working conditions, where tools and instruments should be appropriate. The physical arrangement of production means should facilitate workflow, avoid excessive noise, and improve ventilation and lighting, aiming for comfort. It is important to note that this proposal was pioneering and laid the foundations of ergonomics.
- Economic incentives based on the individual production of workers. Considering the standard time as equivalent to 100% efficiency, the additional bonus increased as the worker's efficiency improved. In this sense, one of the criticisms of Scientific Management is the view of homo economicus, meaning the belief that workers are solely influenced by economic or material incentives. However, for Taylor, workers'

motivation was tied to the need for money, and a financial bonus would boost productivity.

In summary, Taylor identified four main points in the concept of Scientific Management (Da Silva, 2001, p. 123): the development of a scientific method for performing workers' tasks; the establishment of a scientific process for selecting and training workers; the promotion of cooperation between managers and workers; and the division and specialization of labor.

Thus, it can be observed that although several authors had anticipated some of the fundamental ideas of Scientific Management before Taylor, it was he who theorized, systematized, and empirically applied its principles, in addition to disseminating them to the business community.

FOLLOWERS OF SCIENTIFIC MANAGEMENT

Taylor had several followers and collaborators. According to Thompson (1915, p. 263), the main followers of the "father of Scientific Management" can be classified into a group and a branch of this group. The Taylor Group, composed of Henry Gantt (1861-1919), Carl Barth (1860-1939), and Sanford E. Thompson (1867-1949), and a branch represented by Harrington Emerson (1853-1931).

Within the Taylor Group, Gantt proposed a "task-bonus" incentive payment system, where the worker received a bonus for meeting a performance standard. Another significant contribution from Gantt was the chart that bears his name, used to control actual performance against planned performance. Barth, a mathematician and professor, was considered an orthodox disciple of Taylor, helping him solve mathematical problems in his experiments. Thompson applied the concepts of Scientific Management to the construction industry and was co-author, with Taylor, of *Concrete Costs* (1912).

Within the movement, engineer Harrington Emerson stands out, who in 1909 published the book *Efficiency as a Basis for Operations and Wages*. In it, Emerson presented the so-called "twelve principles of efficiency." Although both Taylor and Emerson applied similar principles and methods of scientific management, the central difference between their approaches lay in the concept of "staff." For Taylor, the "staff" was understood as a group of specialists responsible for planning and supervising operations. For Emerson, the "staff" was made up of advisors, more experienced workers than others, but without the deep specialization of Taylor's experts.

According to Da Silva (2011, p. 126), among Taylor's followers, Frank B. Gilbreth (1868-1924) and Lilian Gilbreth (1878-1972), Morris L. Cooke (1872-1960), and Henry Ford (1863-1947) stand out. Frank Gilbreth published *Fatigue Study* in 1916, and, together with his wife, *Applied Motion Study* in 1917. Initially, the Gilbreths applied Taylor's methods for time and motion studies, but soon developed their own techniques. The Gilbreths' main contributions to Scientific Management were the study of human fatigue and the analysis of the elementary movements necessary to carry out any task, which they called "therbligs" (an acronym of Gilbreth).

Morris Llewellyn Cooke, a collaborator of Taylor, applied the principles of Scientific Management in governmental and educational contexts, acting as a consultant. Cooke's approach was to encourage active participation from all workers in finding the best way to perform tasks, which distanced him from Taylor's view that this responsibility should be exclusively assigned to specialists (Wren, 2011, p. 17). According to the historiographical research by Wrege and Stotka (1978, p. 736), both planned to publish a book together, *Industrial Management*, based on Taylor's lectures, which would teach the principles of Scientific Management. However, while Cooke sought a publisher with the book ready, Taylor decided to publish his own book. As compensation, Taylor offered Cooke the entire profit from the sales of his new book.

After analyzing the correspondence between Taylor and Cooke, as well as the unpublished manuscript of the book *Industrial Management*, both available in the Taylor Collection at the Stevens Institute of Technology (N.J.), Wrege and Stotka (op. cit., p. 736) demonstrated that Taylor used a significant portion (69 pages) of Cooke's unpublished book material in his own work, *Principles of Scientific Management*. The authors, when consulting Taylor's library, presented facsimiles of the correspondence between the two. Additionally, they compared and analyzed excerpts from *Industrial Management* and *Principles of Scientific Management* (PSM).

The origin of this collaboration began in 1905, when Taylor was elected president of the American Society of Mechanical Engineers and, in the need to reorganize its operations, hired Cooke, who assisted him in this task from 1906 to 1907. "In brief, Cooke, like Sanford Thompson, was virtually Taylor's right arm and an important part of Taylor's team of associates" (op. cit., p. 737).

On December 10, 1910, Taylor wrote to Cooke:

Since this publication of the "Principles of Scientific Management" is likely to interfere more or less with the sale of "Industrial Management" when it

comes out, I shall be very glad to turn over all of the profits from the sale of "The Principles of Scientific Management" to you. (op. cit, p. 743).

According to Wrege and Stotka (1978), the analysis revealed that, in *PSM*, Taylor attributed his name to a work by someone else. Specifically, Chapter 2 of *Industrial Management* by Cooke was used as the basis for *PSM*, with Taylor, not Cooke, being credited as the sole author. The researchers note that, although this may seem unusual, it was a common practice for Taylor, who frequently published material produced by others under his own name. They state:

Our analysis has revealed that in PSM, Taylor attached his name to someone else's work. As a result, Chapter 2 of Cooke's IM was used as the basis of PSM, with Taylor, not Cooke, as the author. Our readers might assume that Taylor's actions in this case were unusual, but the opposite is true. Taylor's use of Cooke's manuscript is merely another example of his tendency to publish, under his own name, material written by others. In fact, Taylor had a contract with Sanford Thompson for twenty years where Thompson did the 'work of gathering information for writing a book, books, articles, or series of articles for publication, and [...] in assisting Taylor in writing said articles or book.' In summary, in writing PSM, Taylor followed what became for him (after 1900) the normal procedure of utilizing the efforts of others to write his articles, speeches, and books. (op. cit, p. 749).

As for Henry Ford, although he was not a theorist of Scientific Management, as an entrepreneur, he sought organizational efficiency in his company. To achieve this, Ford structured his organization into two levels: planning and execution. The planning level was the responsibility of the managers, while execution was the task of the workers. In 1913, to facilitate mass production, Ford introduced the assembly line, using a conveyor belt that moved the vehicles while the workers performed specific parts of the assembly, without moving from their workstations, in order to avoid interrupting the production flow. With this innovation, Ford's company was able to produce a vehicle every 84 minutes. Additionally, Ford focused his efforts on material savings and improving the efficiency of team work times, unlike Taylor, who mainly focused on the productivity of the individual worker.

The theory of Scientific Management achieved great success in the first decades of its application due to its emphasis on efficiency and the standardization of work processes. However, over time, other theorists, such as Henri Fayol and Elton Mayo, brought new perspectives that

expanded the understanding of management, integrating more human and organizational aspects, which contributed to making Taylor's principles obsolete in many contexts. Despite this, the fundamental concepts of Scientific Management are still applied in areas that require intense and repetitive physical effort.

Thus, although its approach is limited in more complex environments, the principles of rational work organization and process optimization remain relevant in specific contexts, showing the durability and adaptation of some of its original ideas.

FINAL CONSIDERATIONS

The central objective of this study was to answer the fundamental questions that guided the research on the origin and development of Scientific Management, the theoretical proposal of this approach, and the main followers of its ideas. Throughout the analysis, it was possible to observe that, before the publication of Frederick Winslow Taylor's works, several thinkers had proposed concepts that, to some extent, foreshadowed the principles of Scientific Management. Among these, prominent figures include Adam Smith (1776), Robert Owen (1810), James Mill (1820), Charles Babbage (1832), Frederick Halsey (1891), Daniel McCallum (1856), Henry V. Poor (1812-1905), Henry Metcalfe (1885), and Henry Towne (1886). However, it was Taylor who managed to craft a cohesive, systematic theory that was widely applied, based on the foundations of this approach.

Taylor's work developed in two distinct phases: the first, beginning with the publication of *Shop Management* (1903), and the second, with the publication of *Principles of Scientific Management* (1911). It is important to highlight that the term "Scientific Management" was coined by lawyer Louis Brandeis and that Taylor, in his book, used significant material from the unpublished work *Industrial Management*, co-authored with Morris L. Cooke.

Scientific Management is an administrative theory focused on specialization and division of labor, with the aim of increasing worker productivity and, consequently, the profitability and prosperity of both companies and workers.

In short, Scientific Management had several followers who, practically or theoretically, contributed to the expansion and dissemination of its principles. Among the most prominent were Henry Gantt (1861-1919), Carl Barth (1860-1939), Sanford E. Thompson (1867–1949), Harrington Emerson (1853-1931), Frank B. Gilbreth (1868-1924), Lilian Gilbreth (1878-1972),

Morris L. Cooke (1872-1960), and Henry Ford (1863-1947), each making important contributions to strengthening and applying Scientific Management across various fields, from industry to government.

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